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TURKISH COFFEE CULTURE

Abstract: This article provides information about the history of Turkish coffee culture and its revolution and how prepare Turkish coffee

Keywords: coffee, cups, cup holders, coffee jug, chafing dish, sweetmeats, sherbet, rose water, roasting pans, ladles, cylindrical coffee roasters, master coffee maker

Coffee ranks as one of the world's major crops and is the major export product of some countries for centuries.

Although coffee culture at the palace continued in the traditional manner during the 19th century, using coffee sets consisting of coffee cups, cup holders, coffee jug, chafing dish and richly decorated cloth cover, European style coffee sets for one or two people were also used.

One custom that continued during 19th century was the ceremonial presentation of coffee to the sultan and special guests. This elaborate ceremony, featuring an ornate cloth, coffee jug, and chafing dish, coffee cups and holders is described by members of the Ottoman dynasty in their memoirs. In the harem coffee was served by female attendants known as kahveci kalfa trained in the rituals of its presentation. One of the attendants carried at the velvet or satin cloth adorned with gold thread, pearls or diamond, another the jeweled cups and holders on a gold or silver tray. A third brought the coffee jug on its chafing dish, where it was kept hot by embers, and a fourth filled the cups, placed each in a holder and offered them to the guests. The ceremony the supervised by a female harem official called the kahveci usta, or master coffee maker.

How to prepare Turkish coffee

Take freshly roasted coffee that has been ground to a fine powder.

Place a small heaped spoonful of coffee for each person into a cezvu a small coffee pot with a long handle

Add sugar if desired 1 or 2 cubes of sugar each per person, depending on how sweet they like their coffee slightly sweet, medium sweet or sweet.

Fill each cup with water at room temperature and add to the cezue.

Stir well before placing the cezue on the stove coffee should never be stirred once it has begun heating

Place the cezue on a low heat for approximately three minutes, until the froth begins to rise.

Before the froth overflows, remove from the heat and pour an equal amount of froth into each coffee cup.

Replace the cezue on the stove and as soon as the froth rises again remove from the heat and distribute the froth between the coffee cups. Finally pour the coffee into each cup.

- The sultan, sultan's mother and members of the royal family, high ranking members of sultan's household and other palace dignitaries had their own coffee makers responsible for preparing their coffee and caring for their coffee equipment. The chief coffee maker was in charge of preparing the sultans coffee, and responsible for his jeweled coffee sets, which were kept in the Treasury. The post of the chief maker one of the officer of the Privy Chamber,1522- 1566. The chief coffee maker in the Harem, the kahveci usta, supervised the girls who prepared and served coffee.

Coffee drinking had long been firmly established at the palace by the beginning of the 17th century. Statesmen and ambassadors who came to the palace for -audience with the sultan in the Audience Chamber were offered coffee while they waited in reception rooms on the inner side of the Gate of Greeting and the Gate of Felicity.